

Bee honey and green tea as alternative regimes for healing of skin infections, involving multi drug resistant pathogens.

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Skin infections in humans represent a complex syndrome that is, from etiological point of view, often hard to solve. Rapidly emerging nosocomial pathogens and the problem of multi-drug resistance necessitates periodic review of isolation patterns and antibiogram in the hospitals. This study aims to assess the antimicrobial activity of Commercial Green Tea (CGT) hot aqueous extract and Bee Honey (BH) against multidrug resistant (MDR) bacterial and fungal clinical isolates. Clinical samples were obtained from skin of patients suffering of burn (40 cases) and dermatophytic infections (30 cases), attending the outpatient clinic of Tanta University Hospitals. They were grown on cetrimide agar with nalidixic acid to obtain *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and on Sabouraud's agar with cycloheximide to obtain *Trichophyton rubrum*. All isolates were tested using commercial antimicrobial agents to select the most resistant bacterial and fungal isolates. The highest antimicrobial potentials were observed at 25 mg/ml for both CGT extract and BH against the selected MDR isolates (considered as their MIC), recording surviving ratios in the microbial growth of 28% and 31%, respectively. Then both MDR isolates were conducted for establishment of a skin infection on experimental animal models, and treated with separate doses of green tea and bee honey. Macroscopic examination of treated infections showed promising healing rates for both trials, and the microbial growth was highly reduced by the end of treatment course (3 weeks). Both natural products were analyzed for active ingredients by SPME and GC/MS procedures, detecting mainly the presence of benzaldehyde, benzeneacetaldehyde, and toluene in bee honey (10.91, 10.74 and 6.65 mg/100g dry wt, respectively), which possessed a high ratio of phenolics (98 mg/100ml dry wt); and terpenes, esters, and benzaldehyde in green tea extract (33.8, 15.5 and 3.4 mg/100g dry wt, respectively), which possessed a moderate

ratio of phenolics (36 mg/100ml dry wt). Antimicrobial activity and histological effects of both selected natural products were evaluated *in vivo*, showing observable decrease of microbial growth and promising healing stages with normal regeneration of skin layers, while the bee honey was found to be the best treatment applied on the infected area, in comparison with green tea extract. The results of this study suggest that, BH have a promising activity against the tested MDR pathogens of skin infections.

Key words: burn infections, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, dermatophytic fungi, *Trichophyton rubrum*, multi drug resistance, honey, green tea.

Burn wound infection (BWI) is a major public health problem and the most devastating form of trauma worldwide. The major challenge for a burn team is nosocomial infection in burn patients, which is known to cause over 50% of burn deaths. Burns are damage to the skin caused by a variety of non-mechanical sources including chemicals, electricity, heat, sunlight or nuclear radiation (White and Henn, 2012). Infection of burns is common because the skin, a physical barrier against microbes, has been compromised. Bacteria and fungi are the most common pathogens of burn wounds. These microbes form multi-species biofilms on burn wounds within 48-72 hours of injury (Church *et al.*, 2006). Organisms originate from the patient's own skin, gut and respiratory flora, as well as from contact with contaminated health care environments and workers. Gram-positive bacteria are some of the first to colonize burns, followed quickly by gram-negative. Fungal infection tends to occur in the later stages after the majority of bacteria have been eliminated by topical antibiotics (White and Henn, 2012). Two bacterial species, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are two of the most prevalent infective agents. These two species have proven particularly difficult to treat because they possess a large number of virulence factors and antimicrobial resistance genes (Church *et al.*, 2006).

P. aeruginosa are the most common source of burn infections. They are Gram-negative bacilli that possess a single supercoiled circular chromosome. *P. aeruginosa* are facultative aerobes capable of fermentation that live in the human gut. These bacteria are known for their tendency to cause disease in immunocompromised patients, such as those with AIDS or cystic fibrosis, but rarely in healthy individuals (Molan, 2001). Bacterium infections are difficult to treat because these microbes possess multiple strategies for eluding predators, including multi drug efflux pumps, antibiotic-modifying enzymes, and tough outer membranes with low permeability (Van Delden, 1998). As the reports of useful anti-pseudomonal agents is limited (some β -lactams, fluoroquinolones and aminoglycosides, and the polymyxins as last-resort drugs); *P. aeruginosa* exhibits high intrinsic resistance to penem antibiotics such as faropenem, ritipenem, sulopenem, tetracycline and penicillins (Mansouri *et al.*, 2011).

Because there is no ideal therapy for multi-drug resistant *P. aeruginosa*, there is sufficient need to investigate the efficacy of alternative antipseudomonal interventions. Traditional herbal medicine provides several remedies for strengthening the body's resistance to illness through effects on immune system components. The discovery of some drugs from plants was recommended for the treatment of some diseases (Aboulmagd *et al.*, 2011).

Trichophyton rubrum, among other dermatomycosis, is a major causative agent for superficial dermatomycosis like onychomycosis and tinea pedis and is known to account for as many as 69.5% of all dermatophytic infections. Treatment of dermatomycosis is often dependant on the clinical setting, however topical treatment of scalp and nail infections is often ineffective and systemic therapy is usually needed to cure these conditions. Chronic or widespread dermatophytic infections, acute inflammatory tinea or dry type *T. rubrum* infection involving the sole and dorsum of the foot usually are resistant to conventional systemic therapy with different azole derivatives (Elewski, 1992).

Treatment for dermatomycosis varies depending on the particular fungus involved. However, most commonly, azole derivative anti-fungal agents are used, but not effective against fungi in hair and skin, and also they are not so good at treating yeast or bacterial infections. More recently, some fungi show some resistance to the commercially available antifungal agents, which mean higher doses and longer courses of treatment. As an alternative to the present antifungal drugs, newer natural products with antifungal activity can be prescribed (Akiba *et al.*, 2001).

Honey has been used for the treatment of infected wounds hundreds of years ago, even before the discovery of bacteria as causes of infections. In 50 A.D, Dioscorides described honey as being effective for all rotten and hollow ulcers. The bactericidal action of pure honey on many pathogenic organisms including enteropathogens such as *Salmonella* species, *Shigella* species, *Escherichia coli* and other Gram negative organisms has also been reported. Furthermore, honey has been employed to shorten the duration of diarrhea in patients with bactericidal gastroenteritis due to bacterial infection as well as applied to heal wounds like the conventional antibiotics and antiseptics (Karayil *et al.*, 1998).

The current antibiotic-resistant microbial species, for example, *Pseudomonas* and *Klebsiella* species resistance to gentamicin, amikacin and ceftazidime, as well as toxicity to conventional therapy among other factors, have led to resurgence of ancient remedies. Honey has been employed by individuals in this environment for its numerous therapeutic benefits, since as a natural product it produces very few adverse effects. Of utmost importance to the authors is its antimicrobial action (Helbling *et al.*, 1998).

Green tea is produced from steaming fresh leaves at high temperatures, thereby inactivating the oxidizing enzymes and leaving the polyphenol content intact. The polyphenols found in tea are more commonly known as flavanols or catechins, and comprise 30-40 percent of the extractable solids of dried green tea leaves. Green tea polyphenols have demonstrated significant antioxidant, anticarcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, thermogenic, probiotic, and antimicrobial properties in numerous human, animal, and *in vitro* studies (Alschuler *et al.*, 1998).

The present study aims to assess the antimicrobial activity of Commercial Green Tea (CGT) extract and Bee Honey (BH) as alternative regimes against multidrug resistant (MDR) clinical isolates. Furthermore, phenolic compound estimation and Gas chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS) analysis were performed for the most active antimicrobial substances. Finally, *in vivo* antimicrobial activity of the prepared pharmaceutical bioactive substances against MDR isolates, and their histopathological effects on host tissues were evaluated.

Materials and methods

Collection, cultivation and identification of clinical samples:

A total of 40 clinical specimens (burn swabs) were collected in sterile screw capped tubes from patients attending the clinics of Tanta University Hospitals, Egypt. Specimens were immediately placed in nutrient broth (NB) transport media. Another 30 clinical specimens (dermatomycotic swabs) were collected in sterile screw capped slants from patients attending the Dermatology Outpatient Clinic of Tanta University Hospitals, Egypt. Specimens were immediately placed on Sabouraud's media. All collected isolates were transferred to laboratories of Bacteriology and Mycology, in Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Tanta University for further work.

Each bacterial burn specimen was cultured on blood agar and nutrient agar plates. The resultant colonies in these media were sub-cultured on MacConkey's agar. Non lactose fermenting colonies were further sub-cultured on cetrimide agar plates supplemented with 15µg/ml nalidixic acid for preliminary selection of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates. Each fungal skin infection specimen was cultured on Sabouraud's agar plates with 0.01% cycloheximide for preliminary selection of *Trichophyton rubrum* isolates, which was identified morphologically and microscopically, depending on explanations of Gilman (1959); Booth (1971); and Moubasher (1993).

Antimicrobial susceptibility screening for the collected isolates:

Multi drug resistance (MDR) was tested for all isolated pathogens by the disc agar diffusion method (Cursino *et al.*, 2005) as follows: each one of the 40 bacterial isolates was tested against 15 commercial antimicrobial agents, namely:

AMP, ampicillin; CAZ, ceftazidime; CTX, cefotaxime; CRO, ceftriaxone; FEP, cefepime; IPM, imipenem; CIP, ciprofloxacin; SXT, co-trimoxazole; TE, tetracycline; C, chloramphenicol; CN, gentamicin; N, neomycin; S, streptomycin; K, kanamycin; ATM, aztreonam (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK); and each one of the 30 fungal isolates was tested against 7 commercial antimicrobial agents, namely: itraconazole, fluconazole, ketoconazole, miconazole, nystatin, voriconazole and natamycin (Jansen-Cilag, Belgium). The diameters of the growth inhibition zones were interpreted as sensitive, or resistant by referring to Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing; Twentieth Informational Supplement (M100-S20; Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), 2010). Then the most resistant bacterial and fungal isolates were selected for further work.

Preparation of the tested natural substances:

Bee honey and leaves of green tea were obtained locally from conventional markets in Tanta, Egypt. Bee honey was used as a crude substance, and then diluted for further preparations of different concentrations with sterile distilled water. For hot aqueous extract of commercial green tea (HAECGT), ten grams of the powdered green tea (dried leaves of *Camellia sinensis* L) were soaked in pre-boiled distilled water for 5 min., then filtered through Whatmann No.1 filter paper and the filtrate was lyophilized under reduced pressure (Tiwari *et al.*, 2005). The dried extract (1.0 g) was redissolved in 10 ml of 10% dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO); this was considered as the stock solution of HAECGT as adopted by Adam (2013).

Determination of MIC for the tested natural substances against the selected MDR isolates:

Half-fold serial dilutions were made for both bee honey (as a pure undiluted preparation) and the previously prepared green tea extract (dried hot aqueous extract, redissolved in DMSO), in order to prepare concentrations of 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100 mg/ml in Muller Hinton broth for bacteria or Sabouraud's dextrose liquid medium for fungal isolate; zero concentration was considered as a negative control. A previously prepared pure spore suspension of each test microorganism (0.5ml of about 10^6 cells/ml) was mixed with 9.5 ml of each concentration in pre-sterilized test tubes, incubated at 27°C for 3 days for fungi, and at 37°C for 24 hours for bacteria, then optical density of growth was measured by spectrophotometer (Optima SP-300, Japan) at 620 nm for each incubated mixture, and MIC was recorded for each tested material. All tested concentrations were prepared in triplicates, and the mean value was calculated to conclude the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for both tested substances against each of the selected MDR isolates (Shadomy *et al.*, 1985).

Determination of total phenolic content of the tested natural substances:

Chemical analysis was carried out for both green tea and bee honey through different stages to reveal the expected active ingredients responsible for their antimicrobial activity as follows: The phenolic compounds (flavonoids and phenolic acids) were extracted from the honey and green tea samples according to the method described by Kacaniova (1976). Ten grams of each sample were dissolved in 50 ml of acidified deionized water (acidified to pH 2 with HCl). The solution was then filtered with a cotton filter to remove solid particles and the filtrate was used for the estimation of total phenolic compounds. The total phenolic content was estimated using the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method. Appropriately diluted honey sample, 0.2 ml of 10% aqueous extract of the honey sample was treated with 0.8 ml of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 2.0 ml of 7.5% Na₂CO₃. The mixture was diluted using 7.0 ml distilled water and the absorbance was read after 2hrs at 765 nm; the result was calculated as gallic acid equivalent.

Analysis of volatile components of the tested natural substances:

Analysis of volatile components of honey and green tea was carried out through two consequent stages as follows (Wolski *et al.*, 2006):

Solid phase microextraction (SPME) procedure: The SPME procedure was performed using a manual SPME holder (Supelco) equipped with a 65 µm polydimethylsiloxane/ divinylbenzene (PDMS/DVB) (Supelco) coating. Before the each use of the fiber it was conditioned at the GC injection port, at a temperature of 250°C for 30 minutes. About 1-1.5 g of the investigated sample was dried and redissolved in 10 ml hexane, then placed into a 4 ml vial closed with a screw and heated to 40°C for 60 minutes and the fiber was then exposed to honey headspace. After 30 min, the SPME fiber was withdrawn from the vial and promptly introduced into the GC injector under the conditions reported below.

Gas chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS) procedure: GC/MS analyses were performed using Agilent 6890 GC coupled to an Agilent 5975 quadrupole mass detector. The SPME fiber was desorbed in GC injector at 220°C for 5 minutes in splitless mode and chromatographic separation was carried out on a 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm film thickness HP-5MS (5% Phenyl Methyl Siloxane) capillary column. The GC oven temperature was programmed from 40°C (held for 5 min.) to 250°C at a rate of 5°C. Helium was used as a carrier gas at a constant flow of 0.9 ml/min. Mass spectra were recorded in EI mode at 70 eV, scanning the 20-550 m/z range. The interface and source temperature were 150 and 230°C, respectively. The identification of the isolated volatile compounds was achieved by comparing obtained mass spectra of unknown peaks with those stored in the NIST.02 (US National Institute of Standards and Technology) and Wiley.7n. mass spectral electronic libraries. Identifications were confirmed where possible, by comparison with authentic substances used as references and by use of linear

retention indices (LRI). Relative area values (as a percentage of total volatile composition) were directly obtained from total ion current (TIC). All analyses were carried out in duplicate.

In vivo efficacy of pharmaceutically-formulated substances as skin healing agents:

Three groups of healthy mice or albino male rabbits (weighing 18-20 g and 2-2.4 Kg, respectively) were distributed in separate cages of three replica for each group; and marked into negative control (non-infected, non-treated), positive control (infected, non-treated) and treated group (infected, treated with natural substance) for each treatment (bee honey and green tea), for each infection (bacterial and fungal). They were nourished with tap water, standard mice and rabbit feed; and allowed to acclimatize to the laboratory environment for 3 weeks. The animal cages were cleaned daily and disinfected with saponified cleaner.

Experimental animals were brought to investigate the healing effect of green tea extract and honey against both *P. aeruginosa* burn infection, and *T. rubrum* dermatophytic infection as follows: For bacterial infection, The back hairs of all mice were shaved 24 h before burn and their skin was cleansed with iodine solution and wiped with sterile water. The standard 3rd degree burn wound was established by a hot spatula with an identical size about 20% of total body surface area and at similar temperature as described by Manafi *et al.* (2009). After 24 h of burn production, 10⁸ CFU/ml of MDR *P. aeruginosa* were inoculated subcutaneously into the burned area. For fungal skin infection, ear skin of albino rabbits (twins of 2 kg wt) was scratched with heat-sterilized spatula, then *T. rubrum* spore suspension of 10⁸ CFU/ml was loaded on the scratched areas and covered for 4 days to establish an observable infection (Sood, *et al.*, 1967). Preparation of topical green tea extract gel was carried out according to Purushothamrao *et al.* (2010) in the Lab of Pharmaceutical Technology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Tanta University. Formulation was composed of 100 ml of green tea extract was mixed together with 6.0 g of carboxy-methylcellulose by melting in China dish on constant stirring till homogenous mixture. The final product was preserved in refrigerator till use. However, bee honey was used as a crude undiluted preparation.

Healing agents were loaded separately on the infected lesions twice daily; then all animal groups were observed for 21 days. Outlook of the healing lesions, the repairing to the normal skin architecture through topical treatment of wounds and the growing hairs upon the repaired skin were recorded. At the end of treatment, the animals were sacrificed with an overdose of anesthetics and the burn areas were removed for histological studies. The samples were fixed in 10% buffered formalin overnight at room temperature, then washed to another 24 h, in running water, the skin was dehydrated in ascending ethyl alcohol series, embedded in paraffin wax, sectioned and stained by hematoxylin and eosin stains. Histological studies were made at magnification of 400X for presence or absence

of reepithelization, granulation tissue, inflammation, sebaceous units, hair follicles and hair shaft formation.

Results and discussion

The overall antimicrobial resistance profiles of the MDR *P. aeruginosa* isolates are summarized in Table (1). MDRPA isolates were defined as isolates demonstrating resistance to at least one antibiotic of each chemical group of antipseudomonal drugs. *P. aeruginosa* PA7 was considered as the most resistant isolate to all tested agents. One of the most worrisome characteristics of *P. aeruginosa* was its low antibiotic susceptibility. This low susceptibility was attributable to a concerted action of multidrug efflux pumps with chromosomally encoded antibiotic resistance genes and low permeability of the bacterial cellular envelopes. In addition this intrinsic resistance, *P. aeruginosa* easily developed acquired resistance either by mutation in chromosomally-encoded genes or by the horizontal gene transfers of antibiotic resistance determinants (Cornelis, 2008). It has been shown that even relatively susceptible *P. aeruginosa* strains pump out tetracycline, chloramphenicol, fluoroquinolones and some β -lactams using the efflux pump MexC-MexD-OprM in synergy with the low permeability of its outer membrane barrier (Li *et al.*, 1994).

High incidence of resistance of *P. aeruginosa* isolates might be due to the contribution of many factors. These factors include misuse of antibiotics by health professionals and unskilled practitioners, misuse of antibiotics by the public (antibiotics can be purchased without prescription), unhygienic conditions accounting for the spread of resistant bacteria, and inadequate antimicrobial surveillance program (Okeke *et al.*, 1999).

Different isolates of *T. rubrum* were observed to possess a variation in antifungal drug resistance, whereas *T. rubrum* isolate no. 7 (TR7) was considered as the most resistant isolate to all tested agents, as shown in table (2). These findings were found to be in agreement with the records of Barbosa (2014), who detected a high resistance of many clinical dermatophytic isolates against clotrimazole, miconazole, and fluconazole. Ikeda *et al.* (2013) collected fungal isolates from human skin infections, recorded their resistance against four azole derivatives of commercial antifungal agents, and tried new natural products to inhibit fungal growth such as cinnamon, green tea and mango with promising inhibition ratios.

Vandamme *et al.* (2013) stated that the resistance of most pathogenic fungi to the commercially available azole derivatives referred to the high variation in the fine structure of ergosterols in fungal cell wall of different fungal taxa, and depended on the water cell content, affecting the penetration rate and solubility of tested agents.

The selected natural products in the present study, green tea extract and bee honey, gave high affectivity against the selected MDR PA7 and TR7 isolates, recording MIC value of 25 mg/ml for all probabilities, as represented in table (3). This trial can be confirmed by Pascoal *et al.* (2014), who revealed that bee honey has been used in ethno-medicine since the prehistoric times, and recently in the treatment of burns, healing wounds, chronic wounds, and antimicrobial agent.

With the emergence of antimicrobial agent-resistant pathogenic microorganisms, it is reasonable to explore new sources of natural compounds with antimicrobial activity (Lee *et al.*, 2013). Green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) has anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and may enhance wound healing process. Thirty six healthy male Wistar rats were wounded and treated with aqueous green tea extract for 21 days. Microscopic examinations indicated a significant enhancement in wound healing process throughout the whole study duration (Asadi *et al.*, 2013). Honey as a natural, unprocessed and easily digested food possesses pharmacological properties, such as antibiotic, anti-neoplastic, anti-inflammatory, anti-diarrheatic, antimicrobial, antiviral, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, cardiostatic, antitumoral, anti-ulcerous, immunostimulator, antineurodegenerative, antituberculosis and anti-HIV activity. The biological activity of this product is mainly attributed to phenolic compounds, such as flavonoids (Pascoal *et al.*, 2014).

Analysis of active ingredients of green tea extract confirmed the presence of high ratio of phenolic compounds (36 mg/100g dry wt), and the presence of many other volatile components in copious amounts, such as terpenes (33.8 mg/100g dry wt), esters (15.5 mg/100g dry wt), and benzaldehyde (3.4 mg/100g dry wt), which are recorded in details in table (4) and figure (1).

Many studies were interested in revealing the chemical composition of green tea to detect its active ingredients expected to be responsible for its biological activity. Lin *et al.* (2012) analyzed the volatile chemical profile of Longjing tea by headspace solid phase microextraction (HS-SPME) coupled with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS), showing that 60 volatile compounds could be commonly detected in this famous Chinese green tea. Terpenes and esters were two major groups characterized, representing 33.89% and 15.53% of the total peak area respectively. Graham (2012) recorded that fresh tea leaf was rich in the flavanol group of polyphenols known as catechins which may constitute up to 30% of the dry leaf weight. Other polyphenols include flavanols and their glycosides, and depsides such as chlorogenic acid, coumarylquinic acid, and one unique to tea, theogallin (3-galloylquinic acid). Caffeine is present at an average level of 3% along with very small amounts of the other common methylxanthines, theobromine and theophylline.

Table (5) and figure (2) recorded that bee honey was more rich in phenolic content than green tea extract, explaining its higher antimicrobial and healing activity on skin infections, as bee honey contained total phenolics with

concentration of 98 mg/100g dry wt, also it was rich in many other volatile components, such as benzaldehyde (10.91 mg/100g dry wt), benzeneacetaldehyde (10.74 mg/100g dry wt), and toluene (6.65 mg/100g dry wt).

Wolski *et al.* (2006) investigated volatile compounds in honey samples of different botanical origins. Solid phase microextraction (SPME) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) revealed a total of 86 compounds in the headspace of 4 types of honey-multifloral, heather, buckwheat and lime-honeydew. The chemical composition of the headspace was very diverse, owing to the presence of compounds from different chemical classes, for instance: alcohols, phenols, ketones, organic acids, esters and hydrocarbons (aliphatic, aromatic and cyclic). The performed analysis showed that the obtained volatile profiles of the examined honeys differed and it was concluded that analysis of the volatiles could be effective for the characterization of the honeys botanical source. Radovic *et al.* (2001) identified 110 volatile compounds in 43 samples of honey with the Purge and Trap-GC/MS method from various botanical and geographical origins. The authors found the presence in the majority of studied samples of the following: linear and branched aldehydes, ketones and short-chain alcohols.

Macroscopic and microscopic examination of the healing skin infections under investigation (PA7 infected burn wound on dorsal mice skin, and TR7 dermatomycosis on rabbit ear skin) was performed regularly through out the follow up of treatment with separate doses of green tea extract and bee honey, revealing greatly enhanced healing rate of skin layers and high decrease in microbial growth in comparison with control experimental animals. Photo (1) showed completely damaged skin layers, such as appearance of hyperkeratosis with entrapment of hair follicles in the hypodermal fat layer, and severe ratio of inflammatory cells with complete absence of epidermal layer as a common effect of burning and establishment of MDR PA7 infection at the start of treatment. After 3 weeks of treatment with green tea extract and bee honey, macroscopic appearance of treated lesions revealed good healing rates with more microbial growth reduction and normal skin care with normal hair development with honey faster than green tea. Histopathological examinations confirmed these observations, as complete regeneration of skin layers, regular epidermal layer, and high ratio of hair follicles can be noticed in sections of honey-treated skin more than that observed in sections of green tea-treated skin. Photo (2) revealed complete disruption of skin layers with severe inflammatory cellular infiltration in sections of skin infected with MDR TR7 in comparison with intact control skin of rabbit ear. While macroscopic appearance and microscopic examination represented good healing rates after the treatment of infection separately with green tea extract and bee honey; as honey gave faster healing with uniform regeneration of different skin layers and complete disappearance of fungal growth after 2 weeks of treatment. On the other hand, Green tea treatment revealed good fungal growth inhibition and good regeneration of skin layers, but with longer periods of treatment.

Good bactericidal and cytotoxic effects of a honey based gel on a human burn wound model with *P. aeruginosa* were recorded by Boekema *et al.* (2013). The composition of honey samples varied considerably. Levels of flavonoids and phenolics. Sixteen pathogens were antimicrobial agents multi resistant. A single dose of each honey sample inhibited all the pathogens tested after 24 h and 72 h incubation. The most sensitive pathogens were *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Salmonella typhimurum* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (Al-Waili *et al.*, 2013). Honey has shown promising results for its use in wound care. This review is intended to inform readers of the physiological properties of honey and the evidence that exists to support its clinical use. When compared with evidence for current wound treatment, honey has proven to be a safe, effective, and sometimes superior treatment for various wounds (Stewart *et al.*, 2014).

Camellia sinensis is known for its therapeutic properties. Although, anti-microbial properties of green tea have been studied, its role against bacterial strains related to skin infections and mechanism of action is not well understood. Sharma *et al.* (2012) explored the anti-microbial activity and the basic mechanism of aqueous green tea leaf extract on selected bacterial strains. *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Brevibacterium linens*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Bacillus subtilis* were found to be sensitive to green tea extract with promising MIC values. *Staphylococcus aureus* growing in the presence of high-salt concentrations, was inhibited by the green tea polyphenolic compound epicatechin gallate (ECg); the capacity of ECg to suppress staphylococcal growth in the presence of salt suggests that this molecule could be used to aid the preservation of salt-containing foods (Stapleton *et al.*, 2014).

Regarding the healing effect of green tea on burn wounds infected with *P. aeruginosa*, Hosseini *et al.* (2011) recorded acceptable rate of reepithelization of treated skin after 7 days, noticeably regular regeneration of skin layers after 21 days, and complete inhibition of microbial growth. Green tea extract possessed beneficial effect on wound healing of experimental animals, as it gave normal epidermis, dermis, hair growing and delayed inflammation of treated skin (Obaid *et al.*, 2011).

Hazrati *et al.* (2010) reported high affectivity of honey in burn wound healing and good effect on the regular regeneration of skin layers, beside its antimicrobial activity against many fungal and bacterial skin pathogens. Iftikhar *et al.* (2010) reported good epithelization and decreased granuloma tissue as indicators for good healing signs of chronic bacteria-infected burn wounds and dermatomycosis treated with bee honey.

Table (1): Overall antimicrobial agent resistance profiles for the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* clinical isolates:

PA isolates	Resistance pattern of <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>														
	AMP	CAZ	FEP	CRO	CTX	IPM	ATM	CIP	TE	C	N	K	S	CN	SXT
PA1	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA2	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	S	R
PA3	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R
PA4	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA5	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA6	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA7	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA8	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA9	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA10	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	R	S	R	R	S	S	R
PA11	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA12	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	S	R
PA13	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R
PA14	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA15	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA16	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA17	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA18	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA19	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	R	S	R	R	S	S	R
PA20	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA21	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	S	R
PA22	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R
PA23	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA24	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA25	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA26	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	R	S	R	R	S	S	R
PA27	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA28	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	S	R
PA29	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA30	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	S	R
PA31	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R
PA32	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA33	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA34	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA35	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA36	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	R	S	R	R	S	S	R
PA37	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA38	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R
PA39	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
PA40	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R

S=Sensitive,

R=Resistant

PA=*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

AMP, ampicillin; CAZ, ceftazidime; FEP, cefepime; CRO, ceftriaxone; CTX, cefotaxime; IPM, imipenem; ATM, aztreonam; CIP, ciprofloxacin; TE, tetracycline; C, chloramphenicol; N, neomycin; S, streptomycin; K, kanamycin; CN, gentamicin; SXT, co-trimoxazole.

Table (2): Overall antimicrobial agent resistance profiles for the *Trichophyton rubrum* clinical isolates:

<i>T. rubrum</i> isolates	Resistance pattern of <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>						
	Itraconazole	Fluconazole	Ketoconazole	Miconazole	Voriconazole	Nystatin	Natamycin
TR1	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
TR2	S	R	S	R	R	R	R
TR3	R	S	R	R	S	R	S
TR4	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
TR5	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
TR6	R	S	R	R	R	R	S
TR7	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
TR8	S	R	R	R	R	R	S
TR9	R	R	R	S	R	R	R
TR10	S	R	R	R	S	R	S
TR11	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
TR12	S	R	S	R	R	R	R
TR13	R	S	R	R	S	R	S
TR14	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
TR15	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
TR16	R	S	R	R	R	R	S
TR17	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
TR18	S	R	S	R	R	R	R
TR19	R	S	R	R	S	R	S
TR20	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
TR21	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
TR22	R	S	R	R	R	R	S
TR23	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
TR24	S	R	S	R	R	R	R
TR25	R	S	R	R	S	R	S
TR26	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
TR27	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
TR28	R	S	R	R	R	R	S
TR29	R	S	R	R	S	R	S
TR30	R	R	R	R	S	R	R

S=Sensitive,

R=Resistant

TR=*Trichophyton rubrum*

Table (3): Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of green tea extract and bee honey against the selected MDR isolates:

MDR isolate	Percentage of surviving cells (% Optical density)						Extract
	Concentration (mg/ml)						
	0.0	6.25	12.5	25	50	100	
PA7	100	65	67	31	30	30	Honey
	100	69	51	28	27	26	Green tea
TR7	100	73	61	31	36	34	Honey
	100	82	59	28	27	28	Green tea

Figure (1): GC/MS profile of green tea extract analysis.

Table (4): Total phenolics and volatile components of green tea extract:

No.	Chemical component	Conc. (mg/100g fresh wt)
1	Terpenes	33.8
2	Esters	15.5
3	Linanool	0.7
4	Nonanal	0.73
5	3-hexenyl hexanoate	0.78
6	β -ionone	0.76
7	1-Penten-3-ol	0.23
8	1-Pentanol	0.8
9	Geraniol	0.6
10	2-Methoxy-4-methylphenol	1.11
11	2,6-Dimethyl-cyclohexanol	2.5
12	3-Methyl-butanal	2.2
13	1H-Pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde	1.3
14	Benzaldehyde	3.4
15	Benzeneacetaldehyde	1.5
16	Toluene	0.8
17	1,4-Dimethoxybenzene	0.4
18	3,5-Octadien-2-one	0.03
19	Total phenolics	36

Figure (2): GC/MS profile of bee honey analysis.

Table (5): Total phenolics and volatile components of bee honey:

No.	Chemical component	Conc. (mg/100g fresh wt)
1	Acetic acid	1.17
2	Toluene	6.65
3	Furfural	0.86
4	Butanoic acid	0.65
5	Butyrolactone	0.12
6	Benzaldehyde	10.91
7	Benzenemethanol	1.28
8	Benzeneacetaldehyde	10.74
9	Acetophenone	0.15
10	Nonanal	0.09
11	Benzeneethanol	1.28
12	2-Cyclohexen-1-1, 3,5,5-trimethyl	0.06
13	2,6,6-Trimethyl-2-cyclohexene-1,4-dione	0.04
14	Benzoic acid	0.12
15	Benzeneacetic acid	0.08
16	Phenol, 3,4,5-trimethyl	3.4
17	Benzene, 1,2,4-trimethyl	0.03
18	Isobutyl phthalate	0.03
19	Total phenolics	98

Burned mouse skin at start of infection.

Histopathological profile of burned mouse skin at start of infection.

P. aeruginosa -infected, non-treated mouse skin after 3 weeks.

Histopathological profile of *P. aeruginosa* -infected, non-treated mouse skin after 3 weeks.

Healed *P. aeruginosa* burn lesion after 3 weeks of treatment with green tea extract.

Histopathological profile of healed *P. aeruginosa* burn lesion after 3 weeks of treatment with green tea extract.

Healed *P. aeruginosa* burn lesion after 3 weeks of treatment with bee honey.

Histopathological profile of healed *P. aeruginosa* burn lesion after 3 weeks of treatment with bee honey.

Photo (1): Macroscopic and microscopic profiles of *in vivo* healing of MDR *P. aeruginosa*-infected burn wounds on mice skin.

Non-infected, non- treated rabbit ear skin.

Non-infected, non-treated rabbit ear histopathological profile.

T. rubrum-infected, non- treated rabbit ear skin.

T. rubrum-infected, non-treated rabbit ear histopathological profile.

Healed rabbit ear skin, treated with green tea extract after 3 weeks.

Histopathological profile of healed rabbit ear skin, treated with green tea extract after 3 weeks.

Healed rabbit ear skin, treated with bee honey extract after 2 weeks.

Histopathological profile of healed rabbit ear skin, treated with bee honey extract after 2 weeks.

Photo (2): Macroscopic and microscopic profiles of *in vivo* healing of MDR *T. rubrum*-infected rabbit ear skin.

Conclusion

Macroscopic examination of treated infections showed promising healing rates for both bee honey and green tea extract, and the microbial growth was highly reduced by the end of treatment course (3 weeks). Histological findings of both trials showed promising healing stages with normal regeneration of skin layers, while the bee honey was found to be the best treatment applied on the infected area, in comparison with green tea extract. Both natural products were analyzed for active ingredients by SPME and GC/MS procedures, detecting mainly the presence of benzaldehyde, benzeneacetaldehyde, and toluene in honey, and terpenes, esters, and benzaldehyde in green tea extract. However, phenolic content was recorded in higher concentrations in bee honey than green tea extract. Our study suggests that bee honey and green tea have a promising activity against the tested MDR pathogens of skin infections.

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عسل النحل والشاي الأخضر كأنظمة بديلة لعلاج العدوى الجلدية المتضمنة لكائنات معدية مقاومة للعديد من المضادات.

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إن عدوى الجلد فى الإنسان تمثل متلازمة معقدة من الصعب حلها، لذا تجب المراجعة الدورية لتوزيع العزلات واستخدام الأدوية المضادة لها فى المستشفيات للوقوف على مدى وسرعة إنتشار العزلات المقاومة للمضادات. تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى تقييم النشاط ضد الميكروبي لمستخلص الماء الساخن للشاي الأخضر المتاح تجارياً وعسل النحل ضد عزلات طبية بكتيرية وفطرية مقاومة للمضادات. تم تجميع العينات من 40 حالة حروق جلدية و 30 حالة عدوى فطرية جلدية من المترددين على العيادة الخارجية لمستشفيات جامعة طنطا. زرعت العزلات على وسط غذائى صلب يحتوى السيتريمايد وحمض النالديكسيك للحصول على بكتيريا السيدوموناس إيريوجينوزا؛ ووسط غذائى صلب سابورود يحتوى على السيكلوهيكسيمايد للحصول على فطر الترايكوفاييتون رابرام. تم إختبار كل العزلات مقابل المضادات الميكروبية المتاحة تجارياً لإختيار أكثر العزلات مقاومة لكل المضادات المختبرة. كانت أعلى كفاءة مضادة للميكروبات للقضاء على العزلات المختارة ند تركيز 25 جم / مل لكل من الشاي الأخضر وعسل النحل بخفض نسبة الخلايا الحية إلى 28% و 31% على التوالى. تم تثبيت العدوى الجلدية على حيوانات التجارب وعلاجها بجرعات منفصلة من الشاي الأخضر وعسل النحل، وتم ملاحظة مراحل نمو الجلد ومعدلات الشفاء، حيث لوحظ نقص كبير فى النمو الميكروبي، ومعدلات شفاء واعدة بعد 3 أسابيع من العلاج. تم تحليل المكونات الفعالة فى كلا المنتجان الطبيعيان باستخدام الفصل اللونى الغازى، كما تم تعيين نسبة الفينولات فى كل منهما، ووجد أن عسل النحل يحتوى على البنزaldehid، البنزين أسيتالدهيد، والطورولين بتركيز 10.91، 10.74، 6.65 مجم / 100 جم وزن جاف على التوالى، ونسبة فينولات عالية وصلت إلى 98 مجم / 100 جم وزن جاف؛ بينما احتوى الشاي الأخضر على نسب عالية من التربينات، الإسترات، والبنزaldehid بتركيز 33.8، 15.5، 3.4 مجم / 100 جم وزن جاف على التوالى، كما احتوى على 36 مجم / 100 جم وزن جاف من الفينولات. كما تبين من فحص الأنسجة فى نهاية فترة العلاج تجدد طبقات الجلد ونموه بطريقة طبيعية فى حالات العلاج بعسل النحل بصورة أفضل من حالات العلاج بالشاي الأخضر؛ لذلك توصى هذه الدراسة باستخدام عسل النحل ذو النشاط الواعد ضد مسببات الأمراض المقاومة للمضادات فى العدوى الجلدية.